

TEACHING TECHNIQUE SHOW TO USE ECONOMICS TERMINOLOGY TECHNICAL DIRECTION CLASSES

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Abstract: In this article is written about how to teach new economics terminology in technical direction English classes. In this article learner can find new methods and also new vocabulary in digital eco..

Keywords: In English research, economics terminology, vocabulary, value change, Tax, Digital economy, information technology, new economy, web economy, collaborate.

Teaching is a process of mutual learning and this is especially so in a research environment where we explore the limits of knowledge. Research exclusive of teaching is likely to be far less fruitful- this is true of undergraduate teaching as well graduate teaching. Teaching requires one to clearly state and explain concept to the learner. This act forcing function for the teacher to have these concepts clear in mind. Teaching requires appropriate abstractions of concepts to enable meaningful learning the process of forming such abstractions help the teacher great deal in understanding those concepts well and these abstractions ultimately help in better understanding of the body of knowledge, and hence facilitate in expanding it through research.

While teaching economics terminology it can be used several techniques like cluster, step by step like beginning from simple vocabulary till the command work. For instance theme is about value changes in the economics so firstly we should divided simple words and common words in economics.

economics	value
demand	chain
requirement	economical development

Also, before explaining all the theme teacher should collaborate students in two levels students. Who have got IELTS certificates and students don't have certificate in English speaking so it can be beneficial method choosing all students who have certificates like IELTS, TOEFL, CEFR and so on why it is necessary having certificate in technical direction. Because students should have to know English before learning economics terminology in English classes. In the first lesson teacher can make presentation about his\hill achievements:

➤ Doing Business in the Digital Economy

- The **digital economy** is an economy based on digital technologies, including communication networks, computers, software, and other related technologies.
- Also called the *Internet economy*, the *new economy*, or the *Web economy*.
- Digital infrastructures provide a **global platform** over which people and organizations interact, communicate, collaborate, and search for information

➤ Doing Business in the Digital Economy (Cont...)

- A huge number of digitizable products; that is products that can be converted to digital format

- For Example, books, movies, magazines, TV and radio programming, electronic games, music CDs and computer software

➤ Doing Business in the Digital Economy (Cont...)

➤ Electronic Business

- Businesses increasingly perform their basic functions: buying and selling goods and services, servicing customers, and collaborating with business partners electronically.
- This process is known as **electronic business (E-business)** or **electronic commerce (E-commerce)**.

IT Support for Organizational Responses to Business Pressures

➤ Market Pressures:

- The Global Economy and Strong Competition
- The Changing Nature of the Workforce
- Powerful Customers

➤ Technology Pressures:

- Technological Innovation and Obsolescence
- Information Overload

➤ Societal Pressures:

- Social Responsibility
- Government Regulation and Deregulation
- Protection Against Attacks.
- Ethical Issues

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